

UNDERSTANDING THE DIGITAL FORMAT ECOSYSTEM

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Abstract – One of the most fundamental facets of preserving born-digital cultural materials is understanding the data formats in our collections. In contrast to the relatively constrained worlds of metadata and digitised materials, born-digital items can come in a huge range of formats, making format identification a crucial step towards understanding the informational and software dependencies we need to capture to make future access possible. How can today's available file format identification tools and strategies help us understand the formats in our collections, and where are we still lacking ways to gather this critical information?

As part of the *Registries of Good Practice* project (a collaboration between the Digital Preservation Coalition and Yale University Library), we have been analysing and comparing data from a wide range of format identification tools and registries to better understand the current landscape. Combining this with methods drawn from ecological studies of species diversity, we have used the gaps between format registries to estimate the true scale of the format problem. Building on this evidence, we outline how a more distributed and responsive strategy would help us cope with the challenge of preserving our born-digital heritage.

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I. INTRODUCTION

To preserve digital materials, we must understand their file formats so that we can know what software we need to make use of them. Born-digital materials are particularly challenging as, compared to the relatively constrained worlds of metadata and digitised materials that our institutions are more used to, they come in a huge range of formats. But to preserve these items, and make sure we can maintain access to them in the future, we need to understand the information and software they depend on. This makes format identification a crucial part of our digital curation and preservation workflows.

The overall nature and scale of this problem has been understood for a long time [1,2], but most of the subsequent registry projects have come and gone, along with their short-term funding. The few that survive reflect the context and nature of the institutions that need them, along with their own specific context, goals, and influence.

These survivors include the PRONOM technical registry¹: the de facto 'preservation grade' format identification registry. Following the release of the web-enabled version in 2004, PRONOM has become

¹ <https://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/pronom/>

central to long-term preservation of cultural heritage materials. Generally regarded as the gold standard in format identification, this registry, and the openly available reference implementation format identification tool DROID, have been widely re-used and integrated into repository workflows across the world. Still: PRONOM is not the only registry that can provide this type of context. Other technical registries exist with different identification strategies, intended audiences, and overall goals. How do differences among existing technical registries impact our understanding of our born-digital collection materials, and how we intend to preserve and provide access to them?

As part of the Registries of Good Practice project (a collaboration between the Digital Preservation Coalition and Yale University Library), we have been analysing and comparing data from a number of format identification tools and registries. Here, we look back over the last twenty years of digital preservation format registries and place them in the wider context of information resources relating to digital formats.

II. COMPARING FORMAT REGISTRIES

At this point in time, our analysis includes the following format resources:

- Apache Tika
- GitHub Linguist
- PRONOM
- The Just Solve The Problem File Formats Wiki (FFW)
- The Library of Congress Sustainability of Digital Formats web site (FDD)
- The TRiD file identifier
- WikiData WikiProject Informatics File Formats

Of these, Apache Tika, GitHub Linguist and TRiD are all format identification tools that include some kind of format database. The others are explicitly format databases for use by individuals or via integration into tools like DROID and Siegfried.

These different format registries use different models and levels of definitions of format for their records. Most work at the level of granularity of file extensions and Internet Media Types. Others, including PRONOM, are more fine-grained, and seek to identify individual format versions and/or profiles of format usage. But to meaningfully combine and

compare registries, we need to choose some level of granularity that allows us to align the different datasets.

The simplest way to make this work is to discard the finer-grained information and compare format registries based on the file extensions they refer to. However, there are some assumptions and issues here that should be kept in mind:

Some formats might not have file extensions associated with them.

Some different formats may use the same file extension.

Occasionally, precisely the same format might use different file extensions.

Overall, relying on extensions means we may underestimate the number of formats, and overestimate the degree to which two different sets of formats overlap.

1. Overall Statistics

With those caveats in mind, we can now compare these different information sources.

The overall sizes of the different sources, in terms of number of file extension, are shown below.

This immediately raises the question of relative coverage. Are all the extensions known to PRONOM also known to WikiData? Are there entries that are unique, or does the sheer scale of WikiData mean it covers all the extensions that the other sources cover?

To understand this, rather than counting how many extensions there are in total, we can compare each registry to all other registries and count how many file extensions are unique to each one.

Registry	Total Extensions	Unique Extensions	Unique Extensions (%)
FDD	454	44	9
Tika	1,174	263	22
Linguist	1,364	662	48
PRONOM	1,657	77	4
FFW	3,679	664	18
TRiD	3,907	502	12
WikiData	7,274	2,209	30

This shows that while WikiData covers by far the largest number of formats, all the registries contain a significant number of unique records. Even the relatively small (but highly detailed) FDD collection has nearly 10% of records that cover formats not covered anywhere else.

The relatively low percentage of unique extensions in FDD and PRONOM provide evidence that those teams and contributors have done a great job of dedicating their available resources to the formats of the widest interest. But the data also hints at how far there is yet to go: combining all the registries, there are 9,737 known, unique file extensions. This is around six times more than are currently covered by PRONOM. What, then, are the implications for the preservation of born-digital materials?

III. SPECIES ACCUMULATION CURVE ANALYSIS

While aggregating the registries helps us understand the size of the known universe of digital formats, we can go further. We can look at the gaps between the registries to build a Species Accumulation Curve, in the same way as it is used in ecology to estimate the number of species in a given ecosystem [3].

We do this by treating each format registry as a random sample of the whole 'ecosystem' of data formats. We combine them as a series of samples and count how many new formats are added each time a sample is added to the overall set. Overall, the number of new formats being discovered would be expected to decrease as more samples are added, roughly converging towards an estimate for the total global diversity of digital data formats.

The results of this analysis indicate that there are at least 12,000 formats in the total digital universe, and imply that this number is growing significantly over time. Note also that, as per the caveats mentioned above, this analysis should be considered as establishing a conservative lower-bound on the number of formats.

IV. TREASURE IN THE LONG TAIL

Having established the approximate size of the format identification problem, we need to understand the consequences. This is why the Digital Preservation Workbench [4] has been created, which includes a comparative analysis tool that allows those working with born-digital collections to compare their own holdings with the available sources of format information.

The Workbench helps collection holders construct file extension format profiles for their collections or for subsets of their collections, counting how many times each file extension appears. This allows collections to be compared with all the format registries and identification tools, to help understand which of these tools have the most potential to provide context for a given collection.

The example below shows the results for the subset of file extensions from the Yale collection that their PRONOM-based preservation system was not able to identify.

This shows that PRONOM should in principle have been able to identify most of those files based on file extension. However, given that this is the list of unidentified files, this indicates that most of the 'problematic' content is either different formats that have the same extension, or examples where PRONOM's binary signatures are too 'strict' and are excluding files from being identified because they are not conforming to the expected standards.

The plot also shows the potential benefit of using additional registries, with WikiData adding the greatest contribution to extension coverage. However, beyond that, additional registries yield diminishing returns, and after all known file format sources have been considered, 94 file extensions remain unidentified. Manual inspection of these 'unique' extensions revealed that the vast majority of these were genuine file extensions corresponding to real formats that were either too unusual or too new to have made it into any of the available format information sources.

The Workbench also encourages the donation of format profiles of institutional collections. This allows institutions to compare their collections with those of others, so we can start to find our common

ground, but also understand what makes us distinctive.

Initial results from the analysis of format profiles and from exploring the long tail of data formats confirm the intuition that most collections are dominated by a relatively small number of common formats. However, it is clear that almost every collection contains unique formats that are not documented in any format registry, and that the popularity of formats is only weakly correlated with the importance or value of the material. In many cases, the more unusual materials contain the most compelling stories, or most pressing needs for understanding in order to ensure we have the information and software required for access.

2. EMPOWERMENT & COLLABORATION

The problem isn't only about what formats matter, but when they matter.

For example, some born-digital collection materials acquired by institutions were created prior to the advent of the Internet. This was a time of hugely varied formats and media for tasks that have since become more common and standardized. This situation combines the need to understand and build context for unusual formats with the time-pressure associated with the donations process.

Some of these formats might seem unrelated to collection content when viewed as a standalone file, isolated from the other files that make up its context. While these formats may not seem to matter in isolation, they may be critically important to provide insight into collection content, or to render that content at all.

The scale of the file format challenge shown here suggests this problem is far beyond the capacity of any short-term project, and the nature and priority of the work is not something that can be met by a centralized service or commercial product. This is a fundamentally distributed problem that requires a fundamentally distributed response. We need to find ways to empower individuals in institutions to understand, document and identify the file formats in their collections, and let them find ways to share this information among themselves as a community of practice. This needs our systems to empower users rather than get in their way.

As this paper works toward understanding the digital format ecosystem via the species accumulation curve, and models the number of

born-digital formats by way of format extensions while acknowledging the caveats that entails, we might consider the collective impact of practitioners who work with born-digital materials every day. Practitioners have a key perspective in understanding the needs of born-digital acquisitions, and see the various types of files that come to institutions via those acquisitions. With the right tooling – tooling that can meet the needs of individual practitioners within their own context – the field stands to gain important information about file formats and their contexts that can be shared across institutions.

V. CONCLUSION

While stakeholders in the maturing field of digital preservation have created effective methods to manage the exponential growth of born-digital formats, our trusted registries indicate that there is still more to learn.

This paper proposal – that almost every collection contains unique formats that are not documented in any format registry, and those formats indicate a pressing need to build context for the information and software required for access – has major consequences for every memory institution with significant born-digital collections. If we are to be good stewards of our modern digital memories, we need to plan for the investment in skills, roles and individuals that will understand and document our collections as they grow not just in size but also in complexity.

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